

ONLINE COLLEGE PORTAL

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ABSTRACT:

Online College Portal aims at providing the Facility to automate and simplify the smooth interaction between student and faculty. This application do all automated work regarding maintaining and disseminating all information which is extremely useful in colleges. The creation and management of accurate & update information regarding a student is critically important in college. The administrator and student are two major functional requirements in the given system. Proper login with time & role based secure access is provided to admin, faculty & students. The whole system will be controlled by admin. This portal includes forums, term-work management and uploading /downloading study material, exam schedule. All these general details like student name, address, performance, attendance etc provide various records regarding students. This application is helpful in sharing of document with the individual, department or whole organization depending on the requirement. Students do registration on college portal. The admin verify and accept request. All verified student can access the portal and participate in forum.

KEYWORDS: Portal; College; Forums; Automated.

I. INTRODUCTION:

The impact of computer on our day-to-day lives is probably much more so use of Computer and Application Software is increasing day-by-day. Since the automated system is demanded now-a-days, educational infrastructures like colleges needed their manual system to function on computer system. One of such system which is of major importance is Online College Portal.

This project deals with the management of content of an institution using forums, uploading and downloading study resources, maintaining term-work sheet as well as controlling access mechanism that occurs in a Online College Portal. This is often used to support learning in formal and informal educational contexts. A technology-based educational experience consists of several

elements: content, syllabus, roles, sequence of activities etc. That must be aligned with the affordances of the technologies to be used.

Online College Portal is an environment that have been created to allow users, use of forums, to interact with each other. It can be seen as an extension of problem-based learning as it often present a problem with many solutions. This is a type of content management system (CMS). A content management system is a computer application that allows publishing, editing and modifying content, organizing, deleting as well as maintenance from a central interface. Such systems of content management provide procedures to manage workflow in a online college portal[1].

A. PROBLEM STATEMENT:

In the present system all the work is done manually. The whole information related to department is stored in register and at the end of the session the reports are generated. We are not interested in generating report in the middle of the session or as per the requirement because it takes more time in calculations. It takes more effort and physical space to keep track of paper documents, to find information and to keep details secure. When mistakes are made or changes or corrections are needed, often a manual transaction must be completely redone rather than just updated. The manual or partially automated systems information often has to be written down and copied or entered more than once. Systemization can reduce the amount of duplication of data entry. An Online College Portal is a application which overcome the drawbacks of existing system and consist of forums, term-work scheduling, uploading/downloading study resources [2][3].

B. AIM:

The aim of this application is: To maintain all the records in database so that whenever needed retrieved. Easy to operate and reduce the time and efforts of the user. To provide a medium for exchanging idea.

C. SCOPE:

This application provides the detail structure of the college campus and its departments. It looks on all aspects of a college, its students, faculties, Departments, marks. It is the easiest way to manage all functionalities of a college, which facilitates colleges to maintain the functionality related to college faculty and their students.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This project is aimed at developing online portal for college. Once you open the portal all basic information about college is available. There are mainly 3 users they are Admin, Student, and Faculty of the college. The admin have all control over portal, he is a master user. The function of administrator involves verifying and accepting the request of registered student, updating portal, deleting user. Students first register on portal by filling all basic information such as name, email, academic year, branch etc. The verified students can very flexibly login and View Forums, blogs and download assignments, notes, presentation. Students can access relevant resources placed online for them. A separate registration will not be there for faculty. Admin will provide login and password for the first time, changing password for faculty during first login is mandatory. They will have access of forum, with which they can post queries, reply queries, upload assignment, notes, presentation, and video, placement activity. Students will also use the system to read important announcements, to obtain information on assessment, online discussion board for queries and to see the results of Term-work recorded in the system. Each user provided a different features & authorization. They can see the information provided by the student like personal details, educational details, parent mobile number, extracurricular activity or other information. They put online notices, schedule and events so that the entire user can view this. They also uploads/download the information. They can communicate with the Student & faculty through forum. The proposed Online College Portal is intended to avoid all the drawbacks of existing system. It will add some more features than the existing system. The proposed Online College Portal is a cost effective way of doing the manual processes done in the existing system. This helps the organization to win the war in the existing competitive world.

A. IMPLEMENTATION:

1) Forums: A forum is an online discussion board where people can ask questions, share their experiences, and discuss topics of common interest. By participating in a forum, you can exchange ideas, ask questions, and leverage the expertise of other people in your organization. Forums can be stand-alone or they can be

associated with an institute. Anyone can post a topic or respond to a topic in a stand-alone forum, but user must be an institute member to participate in a forum[1][5]

2) Upload Files: Faculty can upload notes, assignment question, notices, time-table, question papers, syllabus and reference book also videos.

3) Download Files: Student can search and download notes, assignment question, notices, time-table, question papers, syllabus and reference book and videos[3].

4) Term-work: In this faculty enters the term-work details of each student and those details will be properly displayed hence generating accurate reports.

5) Access Control Mechanism: There will be only minimum two administrator account. Initially, no other member can access the admin account. Faculty cannot access their account unless the admin registered the faculty. For accessing students have to register and the request will be send to admin for approval, if the account is approved by admin then student can access the portal.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN:

The system consists of three modules as admin module, student module and faculty module. Each module has an same login page that contain user id and password field, by entering value in that field the user should login to the system

Each module is described below.

a. LOGIN MODULE: The purpose of this module is to provide entry to the portal. Based on the type of login, the user is provided with various facilities and functionalities. The main function of this module is to allow the user to use the portal. This module provides two types of login — Admin login and Student login, faculty login.

b. ADMINISTRATION MODULE: In this module the administrator enters his/her user name and password, which enables access to the administrator page. This page consists of two following sub modules.

- Student Addition/Updating/Deletion: Each Student is added, updated or deleted according to his/her department.

- Notice/Updates/Result Generation: On the portal, information about notice, attendance and Internal result is generated.

c. FACULTY MODULE: A faculty member can upload/download the study materials that are beneficial for students in solving their doubts. Faculty member can also enter the marks for each student and thus generate the overall term-work sheet for a particular semester.

d. STUDENT MODULE: Initially the student has to log into portal by filling up the registration form. Once the student's request is approved by the administrator, the student becomes a part of the portal. Student can

download the study material uploaded by the faculty members [2][3][6].

A. USE CASE DIAGRAM:

This use case diagram is a representation of a user's interaction with the system with system and depicting the specification of a use case.

Fig.1. Use case diagram

In above diagram the 'student' class will interact with the login use case for authentication start new discussion, post comments and download files. The class 'faculty' will interact with 'login' for authentication purpose, then the 'faculty' will interact with the use case and 'class' for or uploading files, post comments, general term-work sheet.

B. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

Sequence diagram shows the sequence of messages exchanged by the set of objects and optionally an actor. To access the portal registration of user is done using this registered login and password portal can be accessed.

Fig.3 Sequence Diagram for upload/downloads

A registered user can then upload the files and download files as per permissions. Student user can ask question using forum to which faculty can answer. Permissions are specific to the user such as faculty can upload the document and students can only download them.

IV. TECHNOLOGY USED:

- 1) CSS
- 2) HTML
- 3) ASP.NET & C#
- 4) SQL Server

Microsoft's .NET Framework is a software technology that is available with several Microsoft Windows operating systems. HTML & CSS is the language for describing the color, layout, and fonts. HTML & CSS is used as front end. C# is simple, safe, object-oriented, high-performance language for .NET development. C# is used for connectivity. SQL server is used at backend for database storage, and to update, retrieval by giving query[1].

CONCLUSION:

In the existing system, maximum work goes manually and is error prone system, takes time for any changes in the system. This big problem is the searching, and updating of the student data and interaction between faculty and student available for giving information to student except the notice board. Proposed system gets automated by use of portal resources to be provided online, communication between the users. This paper aims in improving the manual data collection and reducing Malpractice and use it for productive purpose. It reduces manual work and provides accurate information,

Fig.2 Sequence Diagram for forum

so it is better to have a web based system. This system is useful for colleges and universities. It allows student to interact with college faculty and get all information they needed.

RESULT:

Fig.4 Home page

Fig 5:Forums

Fig.6 Upload files

Fig. 7 Term-work Details

ACKNOWLEDGMENT:

No project is ever complete without the guidance of those expert how have already traded this past before and hence become master of it and as a result, our leader. So we would like to take this opportunity to take all those individuals how have helped us in visualizing this project. We express our deep gratitude to our project guide Prof. H. B. Sale. We also great full to our H.O.D Prof. S. M. Patil for extending his help directly and indirectly through various channel in our project work

REFERENCES:

- 1) Nicoletta Di Blas,Alberto Bucciero, Luca Mainetti, and Paolo Paolini “Multi-user Virtual Environment for Learning”, Volume 5, No. 4 [349].
- 2) Tejaswini Chavan, Deb Dutta , Michelle Gomez and Alvino Vaz, *Information Technology Department, Xavier Institute of Engineering, Mahim (W), Mumbai, Vol.5, No.2, April 2015.*
- 3) Ofoegbu E. O. 1 , Fayemiwo M. A. 2 , Omisore M. O. 2 , Olanrewaju P. O. 2 1Department of Physical Science; 2Department of Mathematical Sciences 1,2College of Science and Technology, Oduduwa University, Ipetumodu, P.M.B. 5533, Ile-Ife. “A web portal Architecture Design And Implementation For Private Universities in Nigeria” ,Volume 4, Issue 9, September 2014.
- 4) Tatnall, A. (2009). Gateways to portals research. *International Journal of web portals*, 1(1), 1–15.
- 5) Pienaar, H. (2003). *Design and Development of an Academic Portal. Libri*, 53 (2), 118-129.
- 6) *The University of Melbourne Student Portal Guide.*